

Identification, characterization, and molecular docking of immunomodulatory oligopeptides from bioavailable hempseed protein hydrolysates

Maria C. Millan-Linares^a, Fernando Rivero-Pino^a, Teresa Gonzalez-de la Rosa^a, Alvaro Villanueva^b, Sergio Montserrat-de la Paz^{a,*}

^a Department of Medical Biochemistry, Molecular Biology, and Immunology, School of Medicine, University of Seville, Spain

^b Department of Food & Health, Instituto de la Grasa-Spanish National Research Council (IG-CSIC), Spain

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Hemp
Immunonutrition
Immunometabolism
Biopeptides
Sustainability

ABSTRACT

Promoting dietary patterns in which the content of vegetables is higher than the current consumption of them is one of the strategies to achieve a sustainable food system while promoting health in humans. Hemp (*Cannabis sativa* L.) protein contains bioactive peptides that can be released via enzymatic hydrolysis. These peptides must reach the target organ in order to potentially exert bioactivity and regulate specific metabolic pathways. The peptides contained in two bioavailable hempseed protein hydrolysates (*bioHPHs*) showing anti-inflammatory activity were identified using a transwell system employing CACO-2 cell culture as absorption model and subjected to *in silico* analysis to select 10 unique peptides. These sequences were chemically synthesized to verify their activity in primary human monocytes (assessing gene expression of IL-1 β , IL-6, TNF- α , IL-4, IL-10, and TLR4), in addition to evaluate the interaction with TLR4/MD2 by molecular docking. Six peptides (DDNPRRF, SRRFHLA, RNIFKGF, VREPVFSF, QADIFNPR and SAERGFLY) showed high immunomodulatory activity in *in vitro* and the mechanisms of interaction with TLR4/MD2 were described. Bioavailable anti-inflammatory hempseed-derived peptides were identified, and their activity verified, suggesting the health benefits that the ingestion of HPHs could exert in humans. These findings open new opportunities for developing nutritional strategies with hemp as a dietary source of biopeptides to prevent the development and progression of inflammatory-related diseases.

1. Introduction

Seeds of hemp (*Cannabis sativa* L.) are known to be a nutritionally remarkable food taking into account the relative content of high-quality macronutrients. The protein content of hemp seed ranges from 20 % to 25 %, which is higher than other traditional vegetable sources such as wheat (9.61 %) or oats (13.15 %), and similar to seeds such as chia or peas, and chickpeas. Subjecting hempseed to processing techniques allows the obtention of protein isolates (>90 % of protein), which could be employed to produce protein hydrolysates (Rivero-Pino et al., 2023a; Santos-Sánchez et al., 2022). Investigation on bioactive peptides extracted from hemp proves several types of *in vitro* activities, including antidiabetic, antihypertensive, antioxidant, among others. However, the lack of biological relevance of these analyses because of the limitation of

in vitro analyses highlights the need for using cell-based assays to explore bioactivity of these compounds, or *in vivo* studies with animals or humans, which have also shown the high biological potential of hemp and products thereof (Cai et al., 2022; Cerrato et al., 2023).

The consumption of plant-based protein-derived products (e.g., hemp) is in line with several Sustainable Development Goals, including “Good health and well-being”, “Responsible consumption and production”, and “Climate action”, taking into consideration the sustainable character of this crop production, and the wellbeing effects reported upon its consumption (Piercy et al., 2022). However, scarce reports are available on the bioavailability of protein hydrolysates and accordingly, attribute health-promoting effects to these peptides is not possible. The structure of the peptide determines its stability towards proteases, ability of being transported and distributed, and at the latest,

* Corresponding author at: Department of Medical Biochemistry, Molecular Biology, and Immunology School of Medicine, University of Seville, Av. Sanchez Pizjuan s/n, 41009 Seville, Spain.

E-mail address: delapaz@us.es (S. Montserrat-de la Paz).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodres.2023.113712>

Received 12 October 2023; Received in revised form 14 November 2023; Accepted 22 November 2023

Available online 29 November 2023

0963-9969/© 2023 The Author(s). Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

bioactivity, although interaction among peptides and with other food components have an influence on their toxicokinetics, as well as intrinsic factors such as oral chewing, drugs, or genetics (Picariello et al., 2023). Several studies support the idea that peptides released from hemp are bioavailable, but scarce literature could be found with cell cultures and with a full characterization of peptides subjected to absorption conditions (Santos-Sánchez et al., 2022; Xu et al., 2022).

The thorough identification and characterisation of the bioavailable peptides, potentially involved in modulating physiological processes (e. g., immunomodulation via cytokine release of primary monocytes), which ultimately might imply the reduction of risk factors related to diseases, is necessary to unravel the underlying mechanisms responsible of the response. In the characterization of all the sequences contained in a hydrolysate (usually ranging from 1000 to 6000 sequences), *in silico* tools are being employed as screening strategy to hypothesize the ones which are more likely to be contributing to the activity of the hydrolysate, although these tools also show limitations (Rivero-Pino et al., 2023b). Chemical synthesis of peptides allows to evaluate the potential bioactivity of sequences as single compounds, which allows to verify the responsible compounds associated with the claimed bioactivity of a hydrolysate.

The study aims to screen and identify bioavailable and highly immunomodulatory hempseed protein hydrolysates (HPHs)-derived oligopeptides via CACO-2/primary human monocytes co-culture model. For this purpose, the objective was to evaluate the peptidome of two bioavailable hempseed protein hydrolysates (*bio*HPHs) which have shown to exert high anti-inflammatory and antioxidant activity (obtained with Alcalase and Flavourzyme). Peptides were identified from the original hydrolysate and from the fraction collected after subjecting the hydrolysate to CACO-2 cells in a transwell model. Peptides showing high activity with *in silico* analyses were chemically synthesised to verify their activity in primary human monocytes, while also were subjected to molecular docking in order to evaluate how they might interact with TRL4/MD2.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Chemicals and samples

Cannabis sativa L. seeds were acquired from Sensi Seeds Bank (<https://sensiseeds.com/>). Alcalase 2.4 L and Flavourzyme 1000 L (catalysts) were provided by Novozymes (Bagsvaerd, Denmark). The rest of the reagents and solvents employed were of analytical grade and purchased from Sigma Chemical Co., Bachem AG (Bubendorf, CH, EU), and Gibco (Waltham, MA, USA). CACO-2 cells were obtained from the Cellular Biology Unit of the Instituto de la Grasa (Seville, Spain). Primary human monocytes were isolated from leukopak (Andalusian Public Health System Biobank, S2200035). The selected peptides were synthesised by Fmoc solid-phase method by the Barcelona Scientific Park Nanbiosis (Barcelona, Spain) at 99 % purity, measured by HPLC-UV at 220 nm.

2.2. Preparation of hempseed protein isolate and hydrolysates

Hempseed protein isolate (HPI) was obtained as described in (Montserrat-de-la-Paz et al., 2023) to obtain a product containing 90 % of protein. HPI was hydrolysed following a sequential enzymatic treatment to obtain the HPHs. Alcalase (0.3 AU/g of protein) was added to HPI diluted in distilled water (10 % w/v) at pH 8 and a sample was collected after 20 min (HPH20A), and the reaction continued up to 60 min, and then Flavourzyme (60 LAPU/g of protein) was added, and sample was collected after 15 min (HPH60A15F). The hydrolysates were chosen based on previous results from our research group (Montserrat-de-la-Paz et al., 2023b). The hydrolysis was carried out in a jacketed reactor under continuous stirring at constant temperature (50 °C) and pH. Enzyme deactivation for each aliquot was done by heating for 15 min at 85 °C. The chemical characterization of hempseed protein

products is described in Montserrat-de la Paz et al., (2023).

2.3. Cell viability assay

CACO-2 cells were incubated with different concentrations of HPHs in 96-well plates (10^5 cells/well) for 24 h. The concentrations used were up to 1 mg/mL. Subsequently, the 3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide (MTT) solution (Sigma Aldrich) was added and incubated until a purple precipitate was visible. The MTT crystals were solubilized with dimethyl sulfoxide (Sigma-Aldrich) and subsequently measured with a microplate reader at 570 nm corrected at 650 nm. Cell survival was expressed as percentage absorbance compared to that obtained in untreated control cells. The viability of the cells showed that there were no significant differences in the cytotoxicity of the HPHs at the different concentrations (Montserrat-de-la-Paz et al., 2023).

2.4. Culture of CACO-2 cells and treatments of HPHs

CACO-2 cells were maintained in Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Medium (DMEM) medium with high glucose content, supplemented with 10 % heat-inactivated foetal bovine serum and 1 % penicillin/streptomycin. They were incubated in an atmosphere with 5 % CO₂ at 37 °C and given a fresh medium every 2–3 days. The experiments were carried out in twelve-well plates, seeding the CACO-2 cells at a density of 5×10^5 cells per well. Cell monolayer integrity was monitored by *trans*-epithelial electrical resistance using a Millicell® ERS-2 voltammeter (Millipore). Inserts were used for 2 weeks after seeding and had a resistance of at least 500 W/cm². CACO-2 cells were cultured in 12-well cell culture inserts with fresh medium containing the HPH20A or HPH60A15F at 1 mg/mL in the apical chamber. After 4 h, the content in the basolateral side was recovered in PBS (*bio*HPH20A and *bio*HPH60A15F). In addition, to study the immunomodulatory effects of *bio*HPHs, in the basolateral side, lipopolysaccharide (LPS, 1 µg/mL)-activated primary human monocytes isolated by Ficoll density gradient from leukopak and CD14 positive selection were cultured and then the RNA was isolated to perform RT-qPCR.

2.5. RNA isolation and quantification of gene expression by RT-qPCR

Total RNA was extracted using TRIsure Reagent (Bioline, Barcelona, Spain). RNA quality was evaluated by the A₂₆₀/A₂₈₀ ratio in NanoDrop ND-2000 (ThermoFisher Scientific, Madrid, Spain). Briefly, RNA (1000 ng) was reverse transcribed (iScript, Bio-Rad). 10 ng of cDNA was used as a template for the RT-qPCR amplifications. mRNA levels for specific genes were determined on the CFX96 system (Bio-Rad, California, USA). For each PCR reaction, an optimal volume of the cDNA template was added, containing the primer pairs for either gene or for glyceraldehyde 3-phosphate dehydrogenase (GAPDH) and hypoxanthine phosphoribosyltransferase (HPRT) as housekeeping genes. The sequences of the designed oligonucleotides are shown in Supplementary Table 1.

2.6. Peptide extraction, purification, and sequence identification by LC-TIMS-MS/MS

Samples (HPH20A, HPH60A15F, *bio*HPH20A and *bio*HPH60A15F) were acidified with 0.5 % trifluoroacetic acid. Desalting and concentration step was performed with ZipTip C18 (Millipore), the samples were speed-vacuum dried, and the total protein content was analysed by bicinchoninic acid assay. LC-TIMS-MS/MS was carried out using a nanoElute nanoflow ultrahigh-pressure LC system (Bruker Daltonics, Bremen, Germany) coupled to a timsTOF Pro 2 mass spectrometer, equipped with a CaptiveSpray nanoelectrospray ion source (Bruker Daltonics) according with the procedure described in the patent P202230873. Briefly, around 200 ng of peptide digest was loaded onto a Bruker FIFTEEN C18 capillary column (15 cm length, 75 µm ID, 1.9 µm

particle size, 120 Å pore size; Bruker Daltonics). Peptides were separated at 30 °C using a 20 min gradient at a flow rate of 300 nL/min (mobile phase A (MPA): 0.1 % FA; mobile phase B (MPB): 0.1 % formic acid in acetonitrile). A step gradient from 0 to 35 % MPB was applied over 13 min, followed by a 35 to 90 % MPB step of 13 to 15 min, and finished with a 90 % MPB wash for an additional 5 min for a further time. timsTOF Pro 2 was run in DDA-PASEF mode. Mass spectra for MS and MS/MS scans were recorded between 100 and 1700 *m/z*. Ion mobility resolution was set to 0.85–1.30 V s/cm² over a ramp time of 100 ms. Data-dependent acquisition was performed using 4 PASEF MS/MS scans per cycle with a duty cycle close to 100 %. A polygonal filter was applied on the *m/z* space and ion mobility to exclude low *m/z*, mainly single-charged ions from the selection of PASEF precursors. An active exclusion time of 0.4 min was applied to precursors that reached 20,000 intensity units. The collision energy was increased stepwise as a function of the ion mobility ramp, from 27 to 45 eV. The raw data were analysed in PEAKS Studio ProX (Bioinformatics Solution Corp). The reference library is acquired from UniProt_proteome_Cannabis-sativa_Feb22. The raw data were analysed with parent mass error tolerance set to 15 ppm and a fragment mass error tolerance of 0.05 Da. To account for post-translational modifications and chemical labelling, the following settings were used: Carbamidomethylation of cysteine residues was set as fixed modification, methionine oxidation, and Acetylation (Protein N-term) was set as variable modification. Protein unique peptides was set to larger than 1 and a high confidence score of $-10\lg P > 20$ was applied to indicate an accurately identified protein. This parameter is calculated for every peptide-precursor spectrum match reported by Peaks DB and indicates the statistical significance of the peptide-precursor spectrum match (the quality of the match). Consequently, the ten peptides with the highest value of $-10\lg P$ in each hydrolysate were selected for further analysis.

2.7. *In silico* analysis

The peptides identified in the bioavailable hydrolysates (*bio*HPH20A and *bio*HPH60A15F) were subjected to *in silico* analyses, as screening to choose which were more likely to be bioactive. The tools employed were Peptide Ranker (Mooney et al., 2012), AnOxPePred 1.0 (Olsen et al., 2020), PreAIP (Khatun et al., 2019) to predict the likelihood of being bioactive, antioxidant and anti-inflammatory, respectively, as well as a complete physio-chemical characterization using ToxinPred. In addition, the half-life in blood and in intestine-like environment was predicted employing PlifePred (Mathur et al., 2018) and HLP (Sharma et al., 2014), respectively. All the tools were accessed in September 2023, links available in the footnote of the table.

2.8. Immunomodulatory activity of bioavailable peptides

Primary human monocytes isolated by Ficoll density gradient from leukopak and CD14 positive selection, were 1 h pre-stimulated with LPS (1 µg/mL) and treated with the different HPHs-derived bioavailable oligopeptides at 10 µg/mL for 24 h. Then, the RNA was isolated to perform RT-qPCR. The expression of genes involved in the inflammatory response (including TNFα, IL-1β, IL-4, IL-6, IL-10, and TLR4) was measured as described in section 2.5.

2.9. Molecular docking analysis and ligand-interaction visualization

Molecular docking was carried out to determinate the binding affinity energy of the peptides with the TLR4/MD2 receptor. The X-ray crystal structure of the TLR4/MD2 complex (PDB: 3VQ2) containing LPS was obtained from the RCSB PDB database (Protein Data Bank, <https://www.rcsb.org/>). Ligands and all the water molecules were removed from the receptor PDB file, while the polar hydrogens atoms were added, and the structure was minimized using UCSF Chimera software. The 3D structures of the novel ten peptides were obtained by

USCF Chimera. Then, the molecular structures of TLR4/MD2 and the peptides were converted to PDBQT format with AutoDock Tools. AGFR program was used to calculate the positions and size of the specific docking boxes for each of the peptides. Next, AutoDock Crank Pep was employed to perform docking analysis with the peptides. The potential best docking score determined was selected and visualized via Biovia Discovery Studio Visualizer, as well as the 2-dimensional (2D) and surface annotation of both ligand interactions with the protein.

2.10. Statistical analysis

All values are presented as the arithmetic means ± standard deviations (SD). Data were evaluated using Graph Pad Prism version 9.1.2 (San Diego, CA, USA). There were three replicates of each experiment. One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to determine the statistical significance of any differences in each parameter between the groups, with the Dunnett test serving as the *post hoc* test. Statistics were considered significant at *P* values less than 0.05.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Characterization and bioactivity of HPHs and *bio*HPHs

In previous reports, the characterization of the HPH20A and HPH60A15F was carried out including physicochemical composition, ultrastructural characterisation, and anti-inflammatory properties (targeting murine BV-2 microglia cells, primary human monocytes, and CACO-2 cells) (Montserrat-de-la-Paz et al., 2023, 2023b; Rodriguez-Martin et al., 2020). As reported previously, the HPHs exerted high anti-inflammatory properties considering the expression of several inflammatory genes. However, in the understanding of how these peptides might exert their activity, the underlying mechanisms of their toxicokinetics has to be described. In this regard, their ability to be absorbed has to be verified through cell-models. On top of that, the activity in monocytes was assessed to confirm the immunomodulatory properties that these peptides might exert. The polarization of monocyte-derived macrophage-like cells is divided into groups that are ordinarily (M1) and alternatively (M2) activated. While non-classical monocytes-derived M2 macrophages decrease inflammation and take part in tissue remodelling, classical monocytes-derived M1 macrophages stimulate the production of inflammatory cytokines and reactive nitrogen or oxygen species that support host defense (Rodriguez-Martin et al., 2020).

For the first time, a characterisation of the bioactivity of the bioavailable hydrolysates (*bio*HPH20A and *bio*HPH60A15F) is reported. In Fig. 1, the effect of these bioavailable HPHs on inflammatory genes is reported, evaluated at 50 and 100 µg/mL. Primary human monocytes treated with LPS showed an increase of the expression of all the pro-inflammatory genes, but not the anti-inflammatory (IL-10), as expected in the control. In the case of the pro-inflammatory genes (i.e., IL-1β, IL-6, and TNF-α), the occurrence of inflammation was verified with the LPS-treated cells. It was hypothesized that exposing inflamed cells to the protein hydrolysates would counteract this increase of gene expression. In the case of TNF-α, the effect of *bio*HPH20A was significantly higher than *bio*HPH60A15F, as 50 µg/mL could effectively decrease the gene expression, which did not occur in the *bio*HPH60A15F. Similarly, peptides contained in this *bio*HPH20A sample also reduced the gene expression of IL-1β compared to the LPS-treated cells, with statistical significance, which did not occur in the *bio*HPH60A15F. Interestingly, in our previous report in which the original samples were evaluated in CACO-2 cells, regarding IL-1β, associated with the host-response and resistance to pathogens, no significant differences were found between its expression in cells treated with LPS and those treated with LPS and HPHs (Montserrat-de-la-Paz et al., 2023b). Peptides passing the barrier and those released after the action of peptidases contained in the layer have increased their activity in the HPH20A sample more than in the HPH60A15F sample, likely because of

Fig. 1. Effect of bioavailable HPHs on inflammatory genes. Primary human monocytes were pre-stimulated (1 h) with lipopolysaccharide (LPS, 1 μg/mL, black bar), and treated with the different *bioHPHs* at 50 and 100 μg/mL for 24 h. Relative expression of TNF-α (A), IL-1β (B), IL-6 (C), and IL-10 (D) genes were measured by RT-qPCR. Values are presented as means ± SD ($n = 3$) and those marked with “*” are significantly different versus LPS control (* $P < 0.05$; ** $P < 0.01$; *** $P < 0.001$; **** $P < 0.0001$).

the low molecular weight peptides (less prone to be further cleaved), in the Flavourzyme-treated sample rather than in the Alcalase.

The expression of IL-6 was significantly reduced in all the scenarios (both hydrolysates at both concentrations) indicating that peptides released from both proteases are effective in modulating this pathway, related to acquired immune response, as well as, in the nervous system, to the development, differentiation, regeneration and degeneration of neurons (Tanaka et al., 2014). In the case of IL-10, anti-inflammatory cytokine, the expression patterns are not significantly different between both samples, neither depending on the concentration. However, the response in the gene expression is significantly different from the stimulated cells, showing an anti-inflammatory activity of the peptides via IL-10, promoting the balance of the immune response. These results showed that *bioHPHs* reduce proinflammatory gene expression and enhance the expression of anti-inflammatory cytokines, implying that *bioHPHs* reverse LPS-associated M1 polarization into M2 phenotype. A characterization of the peptides and validation of their activity with chemically synthesized peptides is needed to unravel the mechanisms by which these protein hydrolysates exert certain activity.

3.2. Peptidome profile of HPHs and *bioHPHs*

The peptidomes of HPH20A and HPH60A15F were fully characterized by LC-TIMS-MS/MS and details can be found elsewhere (Montserrat-de-la-Paz et al., 2023). In addition to that, for the first time, a characterisation of the peptidome of the bioavailable hydrolysates

from hempseed protein is reported. The bioavailable peptides contained in HPH20A and HPH60A15F (*bioHPH20A* and *bioHPH60A15F*, respectively) were identified from the collected fraction from the transwell system employing CACO-2 cell culture as absorption model. Furthermore, <1000 Da peptides from that bioavailable fraction were assessed by *in silico* tools to hypothesize and select those which were chemically synthesized to validate whether these are responsible of the bioactivity reported for the HPHs.

In the *bioHPH20A*, a total of 910 peptides were identified (33 % of the original). The average length of all the peptides identified is 11 residues but sequences up to 30 amino acids were identified. Only around 25 % of the sample corresponded to < 1000 Da peptides. On the other hand, in the case of *bioHPH60A15F*, a total of 554 peptides were identified (46 % of the original). The average length of all the peptides identified is 10 residues but sequences up to 22 amino acids were identified. Around 30 % of the sample corresponded to < 1000 Da peptides. The percentage of lower molecular weight peptides is higher in this sample as Flavourzyme, as *exo*-peptidase, would have cleaved more peptides than in the sample hydrolysed exclusively with Alcalase (Mora & Toldrá, 2023). In each of the samples, the peptides which were identified both in the original HPH and in the *bioHPH* are indicated in Table 1 (52 peptides in HPH20A/*bioHPH20A* and 20 peptides in HPH60A15F/*bioHPH60A15F*), together with the *in silico* characterization. Seven peptides were identified in both samples, suggesting that were released by Alcalase, and not further hydrolysed by Flavourzyme, and capable to cross the cells barrier. During the bioavailability assay

Table 1

Physical-chemical characterization, bioactivity and bioavailability prediction of the peptide sequences identified in the HPHs and bioHPHs.

Both HPHs/bioHPHs	Molecular weight (Da) ¹	Calculated net charge ¹	Predicted isoelectric point ¹	Hydrophobicity ¹	Steric hindrance ¹	Amphipathicity ¹	PeptideRanker ²	Free Radical Scavenger score ³	Chelation score ³	PreAIP ⁴	Half-life in blood (s) ⁵
DDRNSIIR	988.170	0.0	6.31	-0.55	0.70	0.61	0.323	0.246	0.238	0.390	832
GFEWIIVK	949.230	0.0	6.35	0.12	0.64	0.62	0.525	0.449	0.209	0.497	788
HVREGDIV	924.140	-0.5	5.33	-0.19	0.61	0.65	0.070	0.377	0.186	0.401	708
NNYNLPIL	960.220	0.0	5.88	-0.02	0.64	0.00	0.614	0.447	0.223	0.392	834
RNIFKGF	881.140	2.0	11.01	-0.20	0.70	0.87	0.798	0.343	0.225	0.436	853
SAERGFLY	942.140	0.0	6.35	-0.13	0.63	0.47	0.615	0.423	0.205	0.398	625
VFDGELRE	964.150	-2.0	4.14	-0.23	0.68	0.62	0.206	0.391	0.229	0.364	757
Only in HPH20A/ bioHPH20A	Molecular weight (Da) ¹	Calculated net charge ¹	Predicted isoelectric point ¹	Hydrophobicity ¹	Steric hindrance ¹	Amphipathicity ¹	PeptideRanker ²	Free Radical Scavenger score ³	Chelation score ³	PreAIP ⁴	Half-life in blood (s) ⁵
AMRNPLAGK	957.280	2.0	11.01	-0.24	0.61	0.68	0.469	0.393	0.235	0.439	828
DDNPRRF	919.040	0.0	6.31	-0.72	0.67	0.70	0.832	0.391	0.273	0.312	840
DESYRQQ	925.010	-1.0	4.38	-0.67	0.67	0.89	0.098	0.447	0.264	0.277	871
DRNSIIR	873.070	1.0	9.95	-0.53	0.69	0.70	0.328	0.251	0.221	0.395	831
DSETVKRL	947.160	0.0	6.42	-0.45	0.64	0.92	0.207	0.300	0.228	0.355	873
GFEWVSFK	999.240	0.0	6.35	0.04	0.65	0.62	0.747	0.442	0.214	0.563	815
GKDNIK	787.030	1.0	8.94	-0.28	0.71	1.05	0.205	0.280	0.197	0.361	854
GKDNIKQ	915.180	1.0	8.94	-0.33	0.70	1.07	0.151	0.290	0.224	0.364	962
GKLDLVKPKQ	997.340	1.0	8.94	-0.21	0.62	0.95	0.196	0.337	0.229	0.409	935
GNPEDEFE	936.000	-4.0	3.51	-0.32	0.66	0.48	0.279	0.394	0.234	0.313	821
HFNLDSH	869.000	0.0	5.99	-0.18	0.47	0.41	0.276	0.372	0.261	0.333	821
IDRPSQA	785.940	0.0	6.19	-0.36	0.60	0.53	0.143	0.344	0.266	0.379	850
IDRPSQAD	901.040	-1.0	4.21	-0.41	0.62	0.46	0.116	0.282	0.270	0.388	837
IKEGDMVAM	993.330	-1.0	4.38	-0.03	0.70	0.55	0.237	0.340	0.197	0.476	832
KEGGVLPQIK	997.360	1.0	8.94	-0.06	0.64	0.86	0.382	0.422	0.216	0.392	861
KLDLVKPKQ	940.270	1.0	8.94	-0.26	0.61	1.07	0.121	0.325	0.247	0.385	833
KNAIYTPH	943.180	1.5	8.94	-0.17	0.53	0.64	0.241	0.447	0.205	0.339	826
KNGMMAPH	885.180	1.5	9.11	-0.16	0.57	0.64	0.443	0.440	0.227	0.434	826
LNDKFKVL	976.300	1.0	8.94	-0.17	0.67	0.92	0.339	0.310	0.205	0.348	833
MRNPLAGK	886.190	2.0	11.01	-0.30	0.62	0.77	0.390	0.384	0.263	0.410	804
NAIYTPH	814.990	0.5	7.09	-0.04	0.51	0.21	0.301	0.471	0.218	0.354	812
NIDRPSQA	900.060	0.0	6.19	-0.39	0.62	0.46	0.130	0.329	0.262	0.409	981
NQDDFRGS	938.020	-1.0	4.21	-0.50	0.69	0.46	0.359	0.316	0.220	0.300	801
NQLDMSPR	960.180	0.0	6.19	-0.42	0.64	0.46	0.380	0.331	0.248	0.327	1441
NRDDMRE	935.060	-1.0	4.56	-0.85	0.73	0.88	0.298	0.304	0.205	0.413	878
NYRNIFK	954.190	2.0	10.01	-0.40	0.71	0.87	0.521	0.419	0.188	0.422	839
PDRHQKL	893.110	1.5	9.10	-0.60	0.53	1.26	0.397	0.454	0.255	0.422	907
PHQEFQ	882.040	-0.5	5.25	-0.28	0.49	0.75	0.391	0.485	0.270	0.351	838
QADIFNPR	960.160	0.0	6.19	-0.29	0.65	0.46	0.751	0.356	0.260	0.341	942
QHRWQSQ	969.130	1.5	10.11	-0.59	0.54	1.09	0.179	0.451	0.231	0.503	836
QNQSPRYS	979.120	1.0	9.10	-0.54	0.62	0.62	0.285	0.424	0.232	0.332	860
RNPLAGK	754.980	2.0	11.01	-0.38	0.60	0.87	0.308	0.381	0.268	0.345	837
RNPLAGKV	854.130	2.0	11.01	-0.26	0.61	0.77	0.244	0.406	0.267	0.348	709
RQNIDRPS	985.170	1.0	9.95	-0.65	0.64	0.77	0.185	0.337	0.222	0.401	924
SEDHTAKF	934.070	-0.5	5.33	-0.30	0.55	0.80	0.329	0.407	0.294	0.331	732
SETARKIQ	932.150	1.0	9.10	-0.45	0.62	1.08	0.064	0.283	0.217	0.361	1041
SETVKRLQ	960.210	1.0	9.10	-0.44	0.63	1.08	0.083	0.306	0.214	0.387	945
SKGYAVASAS	940.140	1.0	8.94	-0.04	0.59	0.37	0.106	0.308	0.168	0.380	838
SQQTRYE	911.030	0.0	6.35	-0.60	0.64	0.89	0.148	0.387	0.212	0.389	869
SRRFHLLA	886.110	2.5	12.01	-0.40	0.52	0.91	0.616	0.400	0.220	0.432	809
TELAHKL	811.050	0.5	7.10	-0.14	0.50	0.91	0.099	0.453	0.281	0.320	832
TKETGQAIQ	975.200	0.0	6.35	-0.26	0.63	0.83	0.034	0.342	0.259	0.344	866
VKEPVFSF	952.220	0.0	6.35	0.03	0.63	0.62	0.442	0.354	0.204	0.384	850

(continued on next page)

Table 1 (continued)

Both HPHs/bioHPHs	Molecular weight (Da) ¹	Calculated net charge ¹	Predicted isoelectric point ¹	Hydrophobicity ¹	Steric hindrance ¹	Amphipathicity ¹	PeptideRanker ²	Free Radical Scavenger score ³	Chelation score ³	PreAIP ⁴	Half-life in blood (s) ⁵
VREPVSFS	980.230	0.0	6.36	-0.05	0.63	0.47	0.501	0.372	0.219	0.421	817
VVRYTIQ	878.140	1.0	9.10	-0.11	0.67	0.53	0.067	0.429	0.175	0.465	798
Only in HPH60A15F/ bioHPH60A15F	Molecular weight (Da) ¹	Calculated net charge ¹	Predicted isoelectric point ¹	Hydrophobicity ¹	Steric hindrance ¹	Amphipathicity ¹	PeptideRanker ²	Free Radical Scavenger score ³	Chelation score ³	PreAIP ⁴	Half-life in blood (s) ⁵
NGPQLIH	777.990	0.5	7.10	-0.05	0.53	0.39	0.416	0.423	0.251	0.377	841
AERGVLY	807.010	0.0	6.35	-0.13	0.64	0.53	0.195	0.406	0.186	0.375	782
LDLVKPKQ	812.080	0.0	6.19	-0.14	0.61	0.70	0.123	0.345	0.262	0.403	820
ADIFNPR	832.010	0.0	6.19	-0.23	0.64	0.35	0.798	0.368	0.266	0.313	826
AERGFY	855.050	0.0	6.35	-0.12	0.64	0.53	0.588	0.444	0.201	0.403	783
TPHWNVN	867.030	0.5	7.10	-0.15	0.52	0.21	0.342	0.533	0.269	0.502	833
TNGPQLIH	879.110	0.5	7.10	-0.07	0.53	0.34	0.230	0.424	0.253	0.365	847
SAERGVLY	894.100	0.0	6.35	-0.14	0.63	0.47	0.250	0.386	0.190	0.353	766
SGFDTRIL	908.130	0.0	6.19	-0.11	0.64	0.31	0.696	0.333	0.215	0.367	559
DNAMRNPL	930.150	0.0	6.19	-0.35	0.64	0.31	0.512	0.379	0.243	0.419	884
DDNGRNVF	936.050	-1.0	4.21	-0.40	0.73	0.31	0.424	0.376	0.245	0.285	848
ENIGDPSRA	958.110	-1.0	4.38	-0.33	0.63	0.41	0.250	0.334	0.235	0.431	789
NLPILRFL	985.360	1.0	10.11	0.06	0.60	0.31	0.856	0.380	0.247	0.496	849

Peptides highlighted in bold are those chosen as promising candidates, based on different factors (i.e., presence in the hydrolysate, prediction tools, molecular features), which were chemically synthesized and subsequently subjected to *in vitro* analyses to validate the bioactivity as single compound.

¹ Peptides were subjected to characterization via <https://webs.iiitd.edu.in/raghava/toxinpred/design.php/>, where the molecular weight, charge, isoelectric point, hydrophobicity, steric hinderance, and amphipathicity was calculated.

² The likelihood for the peptides as bioactive was evaluated by PeptideRanker (<https://bioware.ucd.ie/~compass/biowareweb>), a server to predict bioactive peptides based on a novel N to-1 neural network, by giving scores ranging from 0 to 1. Higher score indicated the greater the likelihood of the peptide being bioactive.

³ AnOxPePred tool (<https://services.bioinformatics.dtu.dk/service.php?AnOxPePred-1.0>) uses deep learning to predict the antioxidant properties (quantified by free radical scavenging and ion chelating scores) of peptides by giving scores ranging from 0 to 1.

⁴ PreAIP: Peptides were subjected to calculation via <https://kurata14.bio.kyutech.ac.jp/PreAIP/>, where the probability of the peptides to exert anti-inflammatory was estimated based on different types of features including primary sequence, evolutionary and structural information through a random forest classifier (threshold to be considered as highly antiinflammatory > 0,468).

⁵ Half-life in blood was estimated using PlifePred (in seconds) accesible from <https://webs.iiitd.edu.in/raghava/plifepred/>.

with CACO-2 cells, the brush border enzymes and transport proteins mediating the active transport or efflux of molecules in these cells would imply cleavage of peptides to some extent, and consequently, some of the peptides previously identified, are not anymore identified in the fraction collected after the transwell system. In the case of peptides identified in both samples, these sequences are likely to be able to cross the intestinal barrier as such. On top of that, the occurrence of specific amino acids (e.g., arginine) at the terminal of the sequences increases the resistance of the peptide to being degraded by digestive proteases, as per their specificity. From the reported peptides, nine sequences possess either at the N- or C- terminal the amino acid arginine, indicating that these sequences most likely would resist the action of digestive enzymes. In fact, it has been demonstrated that Alcalase-derived protein hydrolysates do not completely lose their bioactivity after being subjected to simulated gastrointestinal digestion (Mune Mune et al., 2018; Rivero-Pino et al., 2020). The identification and characterization of peptides prior to and following their exposure to absorption-simulators models is pertinent to determining whether the bioactivity of the peptides is preserved or altered.

3.3. *In silico* analyses of bioavailable peptides

In silico analyses were performed to the all the sequences found (total of 65 sequences), from which seven peptides were found in both samples, whereas the rest were found either in one or the other sample. In the Table 1, the physical-chemical properties (i.e., molecular weight, charge, isoelectric point (pI), hydrophobicity, steric hindrance, and amphipathicity) of all the peptides are reported. In the Table 1 the likelihood to be bioactive, the outcome from bioactivity prediction tools (i.e., anti-inflammatory and antioxidant) and the half-life in blood are reported. According to ToxinPred software analysis, none of the peptides were predicted as toxic. As anticipated from an Alcalase-aided hydrolysis, the hydrophobicity of most peptides exhibits promising values, and as demonstrated in the literature, it can positively correlate with bioactivity (Patil et al., 2022).

One of the most used tools in the field of bioactive peptides as predictor is PeptideRanker, from which according to the authors, a score of at least 0.5 indicates a high likelihood of being bioactive (Mooney et al., 2012). The closest the value to 1, the higher the likelihood. In this regard, the range of scores obtained in the pool of peptides goes from 0.03 to 0.86. The six sequences with the highest score were RNIFKGF (found in both bioavailable hydrolysates), DDNPRRF, GFEWVSFK, and QADIFNPR (found only in *bioHPH20A*), and ADIFNPR and NLPILRFL (found only in *bioHPH60A15F*).

The outcome from the AnOxPePred tool, aiming to identify antioxidant peptides, showed that the sequences NAIYTPH, PDRHQKL, and PHQEFPQ (found only in *bioHPH20A*) and TPHWNVN (found only in *bioHPH60A15F*, being the one with the highest score) could be the most potent ones (value ranging from 0.46 to 0.53), in line with the values obtained in recent reports on antioxidant peptides (Guo et al., 2023; Yesiltas et al., 2022), which were chemically synthesized and exerted antioxidant *in vitro* activity in cell-free assays, confirming the correlation of the tools with the experimental data although only in some cases. On the other hand, in relation to the chelation score, the sequences with the highest score were DDNPRRF, PHQEFPQ, SEDHTAKF, and TELAHKL (found only in *bioHPH20A*). These data are in line with the results obtained experimentally, considering that the hydrolysate which was not subjected to Flavourzyme exerted higher immunomodulatory activity, which is linked to the antioxidant properties of these sequences (Mucha et al., 2021).

In the case of the specific tool to predict anti-inflammatory peptides, the six sequences considered as “high” anti-inflammatory sequences, according to the threshold from the authors, were GFEWIAVK (found in both samples), GFEWVSFK, IKEGDMVAM, and QHRWQSQ (found in *bioHPH20A*), and TPHWNVN and NLPILRFL (found in *bioHPH60A15F*). Some relation between independent *in silico* tools were found for specific

sequences, such as the sequence DDNPRRF, showing high score in PeptideRanker and in AnOxPePred as radical scavenger or GFEWVSFK, showing 0.747 in PeptideRanker and also considered as highly anti-inflammatory according to PreAIP. These two sequences were only identified in the Alcalase hydrolysate, suggesting that it might be cleaved by the action of Flavourzyme, reason why it was not identified in the 60A15F. Other peptides showing high score in different tools are GFEWIAVK and NNYNLPIL, which were found in both samples, and that are likely to be considerably contributing to the bioactivity reported experimentally.

On top of that, low steric hindrance values and high amphipathicity have been reported as characteristics contributing to the bioactivity of peptides, due to their increased stability when interacting with the targets (Mora et al., 2020). In this sense, SRRFHFLA can be highlighted, and in fact, although not among the ones with higher score, shows also adequate scores in the bioactivity prediction tools, suggesting that it might be one of the compounds exerting the bioactivity within the hydrolysate. Besides that, according to the residues in its sequence and the ability of these amino acids' functional groups to interact with reactive oxygen species (ROS) and block their effects, a peptide can have anti-oxidant activity. Tyrosine (Y) in either of the terminals or the presence of valine (V) in the C-terminal have both been suggested to be associated with enhanced antioxidant qualities. These features are reported in sequences found in both samples such as SAERGFLY, which was proposed as one of the promising candidates according to the prediction tools, or HVREGDIV, but in this case, the score obtained from Peptide Ranker was low (0.07), and consequently, the weight of evidence of its potential bioactivity is not increased based on this parameter. Also, methionine (M) and histidine (H) have been described as adequate ROS scavengers, as can be seen in the SRRFHFLA and IKEGDMVAM sequences.

Regarding the prediction tools related to the toxicokinetics of the peptides, the half-life in blood and in intestine-like environments were calculated. The stability in intestine was reported as high in most of the sequences (data not shown), as expected, since it was experimentally demonstrated their ability to cross the intestinal epithelia without suffering modifications. Regarding the half-life in blood, the peptides ranges from 559 to 1441 s, in line with the values reported in literature for other food-derived bioactive peptides (values 800–900 s) (Gülseren & Vahapoglu, 2022), which is mainly influenced by the presence of peptidase in plasma and the clearance of liver and kidney (Ye et al., 2022) and is similar or shorter than circulatory hormones (Gülseren & Vahapoglu, 2022). This suggests the potential of hempseed-derived peptides to act as anti-inflammatory agents, although it should be noted that *in vivo* experiments are required to state actual effects. To the author's knowledge, the hereby identified peptides proposed as anti-inflammatory peptides stemming from hempseed protein hydrolysates and demonstrated to be bioavailable and bioactive have not been identified and characterised previously. In order to validate the predicted bioactivity, selected peptides were synthesized and subjected to experimental assays of bioactivity.

3.4. Bioactivity of chemically synthesised peptides and molecular docking

Peptides highlighted in bold in Table 1 are those chosen as promising candidates, based on different factors (i.e., presence in the hydrolysate, prediction tools, molecular features), which were chemically synthesized and subsequently subjected to *in vitro* analyses to validate the bioactivity as single compound using LPS-activated primary human monocytes. The sequences chosen were DDNPRRF, GFEWIAVK, GFEWVSFK, NNYNLPIL, NYRNIFK, QADIFNPR, RNIFKGF, SAERGFLY, SRRFHFLA, and VREPVSFS.

In Fig. 2, the effect of bioavailable HPHs-derived oligopeptides on pro-inflammatory genes is shown. It must be noted that the polarization status toward the M1 or M2 macrophage phenotypes may be determined by the cytokine microenvironment of monocytes. Pro-inflammatory cytokines including TNF- α , IL-1 β , and IL-6 are the cytokines linked to

Fig. 2. Effect of bioavailable HPHs-derived oligopeptides on pro-inflammatory genes. Primary human monocytes were 1 h pre-stimulated with lipopolysaccharide (LPS, 1 μ g/mL, black bar), and treated with the different HPHs-derived oligopeptides at 10 μ g/mL for 24 h. Relative expression of IL-1 β (A), IL-6 (B), and TNF- α (C) genes were measured by RT-qPCR. Values are presented as means \pm SD ($n = 3$) and those marked with “*” are significantly different versus LPS control (* $P < 0.05$; * * $P < 0.01$; * * * $P < 0.001$; * * * * $P < 0.0001$).

the M1 phenotype. In the case of IL-1 β , a slight decrease of the transcriptional activity in LPS-activated primary human monocytes was observed for the sequences GFEWIAVK, NYRNIFK, and QADIFNPR, although not statistically significant compared to the LPS-treated cells which acted as positive control. The same absence of statistical significance of the decrease of transcriptional activity was found in the case of TNF- α , although most of the peptides showed a tendency of decrease which should be further evaluated at different concentrations of under different stimuli. However, in the case of IL-6, statistically significant decrease ($p < 0.01$) was observed for the peptide sequences DDNPRRF, NNYNLPIL, NYRNIFK, QADIFNPR, and SRRFHLA, indicating that these sequences might interact with the metabolic pathway of IL-6 expression, reducing its release and consequently, achieving a positive modulation of the inflammatory response and a polarization towards M1 phenotype. Interestingly, in the case of VREPVFSF, the activity was found to be similar to the LPS-treated sample, indicating that the sequence has no effect on this interleukin expression. Different sequences might have

different immunomodulatory activity, depending on their interaction with cells.

In the case of anti-inflammatory mediators, in the Fig. 3 the effect of bioavailable HPHs-derived oligopeptides on anti-inflammatory genes is reported. In the case of the expression of IL-4, the peptides inducing its expression were mostly SAERGFLY, SRRFHLA, and VREPVFSF ($p < 0.0001$) and QADIFNPR ($p < 0.01$), whereas the rest of the peptides did not exert any bioactivity towards the IL-4. The modulation of the IL-10 expression could be exerted by different peptides, from which the most active one was DDNPRRF.

In the case of TLR4 (Fig. 4), all the peptides were reported to reduce the activity in the cell model, compared to the LPS-treated sample ($p < 0.001$), indicating that all the peptides are capable of interacting with this transmembrane receptor, which has a key role in the immune response upon LPS stimuli. In Table 2, the results obtained from the molecular docking analysis are reported. The affinity of each peptide with the complex TLR4/MD2 ranged from -12.8 kcal/mol (for the

Fig. 3. Effect of bioavailable HPHs-derived oligopeptides on anti-inflammatory genes. Primary human monocytes were 1 h pre-stimulated with lipopolysaccharide (LPS, 1 µg/mL, black bar), and treated with the different HPHs-derived oligopeptides at 10 µg/mL for 24 h. Relative expression of IL-4 (A) and IL-10 (B) genes were measured by RT-qPCR. Values are presented as means ± SD ($n = 3$) and those marked with “*” are significantly different versus LPS control (** $P < 0.01$; *** $P < 0.0001$).

Fig. 4. Effect of bioavailable HPHs-derived oligopeptides on TLR4. Primary human monocytes were 1 h pre-stimulated with lipopolysaccharide (LPS, 1 µg/mL, black bar), and treated with the different HPHs-derived oligopeptides at 10 µg/mL for 24 h. Relative expression of TLR4 gene was measured by RT-qPCR. Values are presented as means ± SD ($n = 3$) and those marked with “*” are significantly different versus LPS control (*** $P < 0.0001$).

sequence QADIFNPR) to -16.8 kcal/mol (for the sequence NYRNIFK), which is a range commonly found in recent literature for peptides interacting with this receptor (Jiang et al., 2022; Yu et al., 2023), indicating the likelihood of these peptides to interact with TLR4/MD2 and exert immunomodulatory activity. In fact, NYRNIFK was one of the most promising candidates also in the experimental data, suggesting that this sequence is highly contributing to the immunomodulatory

activity of the hydrolysate. In Fig. 5, the 3D representation of binding site and interactions of two peptides with the TLR4/MD2 receptor is shown.

In addition to that, the Fig. 6 shows the graphical representation of the interaction between each peptide and TLR4/MD2 receptor, indicating that different types of interaction are occurring, and that the complex is stable, supporting the evidence that hempseed-derived

Table 2

Molecular docking results for the synthesised peptides including the affinity of each peptide with the target TLR4/MD2 receptor, the cluster size, and the interaction (position, type, and distance).

Sequence	Affinity (Kcal/mol)	Cluster size*	Interactions					
			Interaction Amino Acid Residues	Bond Distance (Å)	Type of interaction bond			
GFEWIAVK	-14.3	37	Ile5 - Tyr375	3.41	Pi-sigma			
			Lys8 - His401	5.38	Pi-Alkyl			
NNYNLPIL	-14.5	24	Asn1 - Ala382	2.68	Unfavorable Donor-Donor			
			Asn1 - Phe406	2.44	Conventional Hydrogen			
			Asn1 - Arg434	2.59	Conventional Hydrogen			
			Asn2 - Phe406	2.41	Conventional Hydrogen			
			Asn2 - Lys433	1.96	Conventional Hydrogen			
			Asn4 - Arg434	1.66	Unfavorable Bump			
			Leu5 - Lys433	4.32	Alkyl			
			Pro6 - His429	2.90	Carbon Hydrogen			
			Leu8 - Tyr454	2.49	Conventional Hydrogen			
			Leu8 - His429	3.01	Carbon Hydrogen			
			RNLFKGF	-15.8	127	Arg1 - Arg434	5.54	Unfavorable Positive-Positive
						Arg1 - Ala382	3.35	Conventional Hydrogen
						Asn2 - Phe406	4.32	Carbon Hydrogen
						Leu3 - Phe406	5.49	Conventional Hydrogen
Leu3 - Ile411	4.51	Alkyl						
Leu3 - Lys433	4.08	Conventional Hydrogen						
Phe4 - Lys433	4.31	Carbon Hydrogen						
Lys5 - His429	3.37	Conventional Hydrogen						
Ser1 - Ser413	3.99	Hydrogen						
Ser1 - Gly387	4.05	Carbon Hydrogen						
SAERGFY	-15.5	40	Ala2 - Ile411	4.01	Alkyl			
			Arg4 - Arg380	3.76	Alkyl			
			Gly5 - Ala382	1.80	Unfavorable Donor-Donor			
			Gly5 - Phe406	5.90	Conventional Hydrogen			
			Phe6 - Lys433	3.58	Carbon Hydrogen			
			Leu7 - His429	3.62	Conventional Hydrogen			
			DDNPRRF	-14.1	24	Asp1 - Ala382	3.06	Conventional Hydrogen
						Asp2 - Arg434	2.40	Conventional Hydrogen
						Pro4 - His429	4.47	Pi-Alkyl
						Pro4 - Lys433	3.66	Carbon Hydrogen
GFEWVSFK	-16.4	42	Arg5 - His429	3.01	Conventional Hydrogen			
			Gly1 - Lys360	2.52	Conventional Hydrogen			

Table 2 (continued)

Sequence	Affinity (Kcal/mol)	Cluster size*	Interactions					
			Interaction Amino Acid Residues	Bond Distance (Å)	Type of interaction bond			
NYRNIFK	-16.8	19	Gly1 - Ser386	3.71	Carbon Hydrogen			
			Phe2 - Arg434	2.20	Conventional Hydrogen			
			Ser6 - Lys433	2.33	Conventional Hydrogen			
			Ser6 - His429	2.74	Conventional Hydrogen			
			Phe7 - Lys433	3.41	Carbon Hydrogen			
			Phe7 - His429	3.38	Carbon Hydrogen			
			Asn1 - Asn1	3.98	Unfavorable Positive-Positive			
			Lys433 - Asn1	4.91	Unfavorable Positive-Positive			
			Arg434 - Ile5	5.10	Pi-Alkyl			
			Phe6 - His429	2.20	Conventional Hydrogen			
			His429 - Lys7	5.40	Alkyl			
			QADIFNPR	-12.8	42	Lys458 - Asp3	1.80	Conventional Hydrogen
						Arg434 - Phe5	1.11	Unfavorable Bump
						Arg434 - Asn6	3.52	Carbon Hydrogen
Lys433 - Pro7	5.17	Pi-Alkyl						
His429 - Pro7	3.34	Carbon Hydrogen						
His429 - Arg8	2.38	Conventional Hydrogen						
Lys433 - Arg8	2.63	Conventional Hydrogen						
Arg8 - Thr431	2.65	Hydrogen						
Arg8 - Asn456	2.65	Unfavorable Bump						
SRRFHLA	-13.4	60				Ser1 - Gly361	2.69	Conventional Hydrogen
			Ser1 - Arg434	5.40	Unfavorable Positive-Positive			
			Ser1 - Arg434	1.82	Conventional Hydrogen			
			Arg2 - Arg434	2.72	Conventional Hydrogen			
			Arg2 - Arg434	4.01	Alkyl			
			Arg3 - Arg380	4.89	Alkyl			
			Arg434 - Ala7	2.02	Conventional Hydrogen			
			Ala7 - Tyr454	5.33	Pi-Alkyl			
			VREPVSFS	-13	31	Val1 - Gly361	2.36	Unfavorable Bump
						Val1 - Lys360	3.95	Unfavorable Bump
Val1 - Lys360	1.62	Unfavorable Bump						
Val1 - Lys360	4.31	Alkyl						
Val1 - Lys360	4.66	Unfavorable Positive-Positive						
Arg434 - Arg2	5.07	Alkyl						
Met358 - Arg2	1.66	Conventional Hydrogen						
Arg434 - Arg434								

(continued on next page)

Table 2 (continued)

Sequence	Affinity (Kcal/mol)	Cluster size*	Interactions		
			Interaction Amino Acid Residues	Bond Distance (Å)	Type of interaction bond
			Pro4 - Arg434	3.29	Unfavorable Donor-Donor
			Pro4 - Arg434	4.82	Alkyl
			Pro4 - Ile411	5.36	Alkyl
			Pro4 - Lys433	4.30	Alkyl
			Pro4 - Lys433	3.65	Carbon Hydrogen
			Val5 - His429	3.91	Pi-Alkyl
			Ser7 - His429	3.72	Carbon Hydrogen
			Ser7 - Tyr454	3.16	Conventional Hydrogen
			Phe8 - Asn456	2.42	Conventional Hydrogen
			Phe8 - Asn456	3.29	Carbon Hydrogen
			Phe8 - Gly478	1.93	Unfavorable Bump

*Cluster size refers to the number of repetitions of docking simulations that coincide in the same structure.

peptides are responsible for an immunomodulatory activity based on their interaction with this receptor. As it can be observed, most of the interaction are conventional hydrogen bonds, which according to the functional group of amino acids, is the most likely to occur and stabilise the interaction (Hubbard & Kamran Haider, 2010). On top of that, following this molecular docking analysis of peptides with the receptor, the same analysis was also carried out with the LPS ligand in two conditions: i) the evaluation of the affinity energy of TLR4/MD2-LPS

complex; and ii) TLR4/MD2-NNYNLPIL complex, used as “receptor”, interacting with LPS, to evaluate whether there were differences in the affinity energy with TLR4/MD2-LPS complex. The results of these studies corroborated the immunomodulatory effect of the peptide reported experimentally with the *in vitro* studies in primary human monocytes, since in presence of the peptide, the binding affinity was lower (data not shown).

To sum up, pro-inflammatory gene expression was downregulated following peptide's exposure, compared to LPS-treated cells, especially with DDNPRRF, NNYNLPIL, and NYRNIFK. In contrast, anti-inflammatory IL-4 and IL-10 were upregulated following peptide's exposure, compared to LPS-treated cells, mainly with QADIFNPR and SAERGFY. However, there is still much to discover in the discipline of bioactive peptide research. To describe a protein hydrolysate and deem it a functional food, certain restrictions (such as determining the destiny of peptides and their interactions) must be addressed, and improved methodologies (peptidomics, *in silico* prediction tools, etc.) must be developed. Studies in humans to determine whether the peptides have health benefits as well as investigations in animal models to clarify the underlying mechanisms by which these peptides would exert *in vivo* activity are still missing.

4. Conclusions

The obtention of protein hydrolysates containing potentially bioactive peptides via enzymatic hydrolysis is a sustainable strategy to enhance the health-promoting activity of vegetable proteins. A protein isolate obtained from hempseeds was subjected hydrolysis with Alcalase and Flavourzyme to obtain two hydrolysates with anti-inflammatory activity. Hydrolysates were subjected to bioavailability assays and peptides able to cross CACO-2 cells were identified by LC-TIMS-MS/MS. *In silico* analyses were carried out as screening to select candidates of bioactive peptides, whose bioactivity was evaluated using the chemically synthetic sequences. Pro-inflammatory gene expression was downregulated following peptide's exposure, compared to LPS-treated

Fig. 5. Visualisation of the structures of peptides using Biovia Discovery Studio Visualizer. (A) TLR4/MD2-GFEWIAVK binding site and their interactions; (B) TLR4/MD2-NNYNLPIL binding site and their interactions. (C) GFEWIAVK interactions with the atoms involved in the binding site of TLR4/MD2 complex and (D) NNYNLPIL interactions with the atoms involved in the pocket-binding site of TLR4/MD2 complex. NNYNLPIL binding site is the same to the others 8 peptides (DDNPRRF, GFEWVSFK, NYRNIFK, QADIFNPR, RNIFKGF, SAERGFY, SRRFHLA, and VREPVFSF) and is shown as representative interaction.

Fig. 6. 2D residues diagram analysis for the peptides with their respective interaction bonds with TLR4/MD2 visualized using Biovia Discovery Studio Visualizer.

cells, especially with DDNPRRF, NNYNLPIL, and NYRNIFFK. In contrast, anti-inflammatory IL-4 and IL-10 were upregulated following peptide's exposure, compared to LPS-treated cells, mainly with QADIFNPR, VREPVFSF and SAERGFLY. Molecular docking analyses showed that there is an interaction through different type of bonds between the peptides and the TLR4 receptor. Peptides targeting different inflammatory genes (DDNPRRF, SRRFHLA, RNIFKGF, VREPVFSF, QADIFNPR and SAERGFLY) were proposed as the most bioactive sequences in the hemp-derived hydrolysates. Hemp bioactive peptides have shown that they can interact with the immune system through different pathways to regulate inflammation response. However, *in vivo* studies confirming this bioactivity are still needed, in order to introduce hempseed-derived products as healthy products and promote its consumption in humans.

Funding

This research was funded by grant P20_00661 from the Andalusian Plan for Research, Development, and Innovation (PAIDI) 2020 and by grant US-1381492 from the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF).

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Maria C. Millan-Linares: Conceptualization, Funding acquisition. **Fernando Rivero-Pino:** Formal analysis. **Teresa Gonzalez-de la Rosa:** Methodology. **Alvaro Villanueva:** Methodology. **Sergio Montserrat-de la Paz:** Conceptualization, Resources, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Acknowledgments

Fernando Rivero-Pino acknowledges his postdoctoral contract supported by TED2021-130521A-I00 (Ministry of Science and Innovation, Government of Spain) into the Recovery, Transformation, and Resilience Plan funding by NextGenerationEU. Teresa Gonzalez-de la Rosa acknowledges his contract supported by the "Programa Investigo" funded by the European Union – Next Generation EU. The authors thank Carlos Fuentes from the Proteomics Unit of the Central Research Support Service of Cordoba University (UCO) for its technical assistance during the fulfilment of this work.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodres.2023.113712>.

References

- Cai, Y., Zhang, L., Zhang, Y., & Lu, R. (2022). Plant-Derived Exosomes as A Drug-Delivery Approach for the Treatment of Inflammatory Bowel Disease and Colitis-Associated Cancer. *Pharmaceutics*, 14(4). <https://doi.org/10.3390/pharmaceutics14040822>
- Cerrato, A., Lammi, C., Capriotti, A. L., Bollati, C., Cavaliere, C., Montone, C. M., ... Laganà, A. (2023). Isolation and functional characterization of hemp seed protein-derived short- and medium-chain peptide mixtures with multifunctional properties for metabolic syndrome prevention. *Food Research International*, 163. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodres.2022.112219>
- Gülseren, İ., & Vahapoglu, B. (2022). The Stability of Food Bioactive Peptides in Blood: An Overview. *International Journal of Peptide Research and Therapeutics*, 28, 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10989-021-10321-w>
- Guo, Z., Yang, Y., Hu, B., Zhu, L., Liu, C., Li, M., ... Zhang, L. (2023). The Bioaccessibility of Yak Bone Collagen Hydrolysates: Focus on Analyzing the Variation Regular of Peptides and Free Amino Acids. *Foods*, 12(5). <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods12051003>
- Hubbard, R. E., & Kamran Haider, M. (2010). Hydrogen Bonds in Proteins: Role and Strength. *ELS, February*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9780470015902.a0003011.pub2>
- Jiang, W., Ren, K., Yang, Z., Fang, Z., Li, Y., Xiang, X., & Song, Y. (2022). Purification, Identification and Molecular Docking of Immunomodulatory Peptides from the Heads of *Litopenaeus vannamei*. *Foods*, 11(3309). doi.org/10.3390/foods11203309
- Khatun, M. S., Hasan, M. M., & Kurata, H. (2019). PreAIP: Computational prediction of anti-inflammatory peptides by integrating multiple complementary features. *Frontiers in Genetics*, 10. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fgene.2019.00129>
- Mathur, D., Singh, S., Mehta, A., Agrawal, P., & Raghava, G. P. S. (2018). In silico approaches for predicting the half-life of natural and modified peptides in blood. *PLoS ONE*, 13(6), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0196829>
- Montserrat-de-la-Paz, S., Rivero-Pino, F., Villanueva, A., Toscano-Sanchez, R., Martín, M. E., Millan, F., & Millan-Linares, M. C. (2023). Nutritional composition, ultrastructural characterization, and peptidome profile of antioxidant hemp protein hydrolysates. *Food Bioscience*, 53, Article 102561. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fbio.2023.102561>
- Montserrat-de-la-Paz, S., Villanueva, A., Millán, F., Martín-Santiago, V., Rivero-Pino, F., & Millán-Linares, M. C. (2023). Production and identification of immunomodulatory peptides in intestine cells obtained from hemp industrial by-products. *Food Research International*, 174, Article 113616. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodres.2023.113616>
- Mooney, C., Haslam, N. J., Pollastris, G., & Shields, D. C. (2012). Towards the Improved Discovery and Design of Functional Peptides: Common Features of Diverse Classes Permit Generalized Prediction of Bioactivity. *PLoS ONE*, 7, e45012.
- Mora, L., González-Rogel, D., Heres, A., & Toldrá, F. (2020). Iberian dry-cured ham as a potential source of α -glucosidase-inhibitory peptides. *Journal of Functional Foods*, 67, Article 103840. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jff.2020.103840>
- Mora, L., & Toldrá, F. (2023). Advanced enzymatic hydrolysis of food proteins for the production of bioactive peptides. *Current Opinion in Food Science*, 49, Article 100973. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cofs.2022.100973>
- Mucha, P., Skoczynska, A., Malecka, M., Hikiş, P., & Budzisz, E. (2021). Overview of the antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activities of selected plant compounds and their metal ions complexes. *Molecules*, 26(16). <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules26164886>
- Mune Mune, M. A., Minka, S. R., & Henle, T. (2018). Investigation on antioxidant, angiotensin converting enzyme and dipeptidyl peptidase IV inhibitory activity of Bambara bean protein hydrolysates. *Food Chemistry*, 250, 162–169. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2018.01.001>
- Olsen, T. H., Yesiltas, B., Marin, F. I., Pertseva, M., García-Moreno, P. J., Gregersen, S., ... Marcatili, P. (2020). AnOxPePred: Using deep learning for the prediction of antioxidative properties of peptides. *Scientific Reports*, 10(1), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-78319-w>
- Patil, P. J., Usman, M., Zhang, C., Mehmood, A., Zhou, M., Teng, C., & Li, X. (2022). An updated review on food-derived bioactive peptides: Focus on the regulatory requirements, safety, and bioavailability. *Comprehensive Reviews in Food Science and Food Safety*, 21(2), 1732–1776. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1541-4337.12911>
- Picariello, G., Siano, F., Di Stasio, L., Mamone, G., Addeo, F., & Ferranti, P. (2023). Structural properties of food proteins underlying stability or susceptibility to human gastrointestinal digestion. *Current Opinion in Food Science*, 50, Article 100992. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cofs.2023.100992>
- Piercy, E., Verstraete, W., Ellis, P. R., Banks, M., Rockström, J., Smith, P., ... Guo, M. (2022). A sustainable waste-to-protein system to maximise waste resource utilisation for developing food- and feed-grade protein solutions. *Green Chemistry*, 25(3), 808–832. <https://doi.org/10.1039/d2gc03095k>
- Rivero-Pino, F., Espejo-Carpio, F. J., & Guadix, E. M. (2020). Production and identification of dipeptidyl peptidase IV (DPP-IV) inhibitory peptides from discarded Sardine pilchardus protein. *Food Chemistry*, 328, Article 127096. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2020.127096>
- Rivero-Pino, F., Millan-Linares, M. C., & Montserrat-de-la-Paz, S. (2023a). Hemp Protein. In *Sustainable Food Science: A Comprehensive Approach*. Elsevier. 10.1016/B978-0-12-823960-5.00014-7.
- Rivero-Pino, F., Millan-Linares, M. C., & Montserrat-de-la-Paz, S. (2023b). Strengths and limitations of in silico tools to assess physicochemical properties, bioactivity, and bioavailability of food-derived peptides. *Trends in Food Science & Technology*, 138, 433–440. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tifs.2023.06.023>
- Rodríguez-Martín, N. M., Montserrat-De la Paz, S., Toscano, R., Grao-Cruces, E., Villanueva, A., Pedroche, J., ... Millan-Linares, M. C. (2020). Hemp (*Cannabis sativa* L.) protein hydrolysates promote anti-inflammatory response in primary human monocytes. *Biomolecules*, 10(5). <https://doi.org/10.3390/biom10050803>
- Santos-Sánchez, G., Álvarez-López, A. I., Ponce-España, E., Carrillo-Vico, A., Bollati, C., Bartolomei, M., ... Cruz-Chamorro, I. (2022). Hempseed (*Cannabis sativa*) protein hydrolysates: A valuable source of bioactive peptides with pleiotropic health-promoting effects. *Trends in Food Science and Technology*, 127, 303–318. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tifs.2022.06.005>
- Sharma, A., Singla, D., Rashid, M., & Raghava, G. P. S. (2014). Designing of peptides with desired half-life in intestine-like environment. *BMC Bioinformatics*, 15(1), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2105-15-282>
- Tanaka, T., Narazaki, M., & Kishimoto, T. (2014). *patterns (DAMPs), which are released from damaged or dying cells in noninfectious inflammations such as burn or trauma*,

- directly or indirectly promote inflammation. During sterile surgical operations, an increase in serum IL66 levels precedes elevation of. 6(Kishimoto 1989), 1–16.
- Xu, Y., Sismour, E., Britland, J. W., Sellers, A., Abraha-Eyob, Z., Yousuf, A., ... Zhao, W. (2022). Physicochemical, Structural, and Functional Properties of Hemp Protein vs Several Commercially Available Plant and Animal Proteins: A Comparative Study. *ACS Food Science & Technology*. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsfoodscitech.2c00250>
- Ye, H., Tao, X., Zhang, W., Chen, Y., Yu, Q., & Xie, J. (2022). Food-derived bioactive peptides: Production, biological activities, opportunities and challenges. *Journal of Future Foods*, 2(4), 294–306. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfutfo.2022.08.002>
- Yesiltas, B., García-Moreno, P. J., Gregersen, S., Olsen, T. H., Jones, N. C., Hoffmann, S. V., ... Jacobsen, C. (2022). Antioxidant peptides derived from potato, seaweed, microbial and spinach proteins: Oxidative stability of 5% fish oil-in-water emulsions. *Food Chemistry*, 385. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2022.132699>
- Yu, Z., Wang, Y., Shuiian, D., Liu, J., & Zhao, W. (2023). Identification and Molecular Mechanism of Novel Immunomodulatory Peptides from Gelatin Hydrolysates: Molecular Docking, Dynamic Simulation, and Cell Experiments. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 71(6), 2924–2934. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jafc.2c06982>